

The High Temperature Creep of Dispersion Strengthened Ni-Al₂O₃ Alloy

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to understand the high temperature creep behavior of dispersion strengthened Ni-Al₂O₃ alloy. The Ni-Al₂O₃ sample was prepared by mechanically blending γ -Al₂O₃ with nickel powders, using a high speed mixer, followed by isostatic pressing, sintering in a hydrogen atmosphere for 20 hrs at 1000°C, and extruding at about 1100°C. The extruded samples were annealed for 5 hrs at 1200°C, and used as creep test specimens. The creep tests were carried out over a temperature range of 800-1100°C under the applied stresses of 20-50 MPa. The relation of the creep behavior to stress and temperature were clarified by testing under the various conditions. The dislocation structure in the Ni matrix was observed by electron microscope.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, an oxide-dispersion strengthened nickel base super alloy has been developed as an advanced material for gas turbine blades (1). It is characterized by high creep and rupture strength as well as excellent corrosion resistance. The object of this study is to clarify how the creep and rupture strength of this dispersion strengthened type changes with stress or temperature; furthermore, how dislocation structure varies with creep.

EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

Sample

The Ni-1%Al₂O₃ samples used for this study were prepared as follows; blending Ni powder having a mean particle size of 3 μ m with γ -Al₂O₃ of 0.03 μ m by high speed mixer \rightarrow packing the blended powder into a rubber container \rightarrow isostatical pressing under a stress of 98 MPa \rightarrow sintering in flowing hydrogen gas for 20 hrs at 1000°C \rightarrow sealing sintered sample into steel sheath \rightarrow extruding at extrusion ratio of about 30 : 1 at 1100°C. Specimens for the creep and rupture tests were cut away from the extruded material and annealed in a vacuum for 5 hrs at 1200°C in order to control crystal structure. They were shaped into specimen of 40 mm length in parallel part and 4 mm ϕ in diameter.

Creep and rupture test

Creep rupture strength was measured at every 50°C interval in the range 800-1100°C under the applied stresses of 20-50 MPa. Temperature was controlled within ±5°C. Stress was applied by putting measured weight on the platform set vertically on the longitudinal extension of the specimen. Creep deformation was read out by a dial gauge having the precision of 1 μm to one division.

Figure 1 shows the creep strain/time curve of the extruded and the annealed specimens measured under a starting applied stress of 39.2 MPa at 800°C. The strain of the extruded specimen was more than twice as much as the annealed specimen and the strain rate was also faster, while the strain of the annealed specimen did not reach 0.7% even after 7000 hrs. These samples did not seem to rupture after longer period of creep, so the measurement was discontinued.

Figure 2 shows log stress vs log rupture life (hr) under the stresses of 20-50 MPa at the range 900-1100°C. From this graph, the relation of $t \propto \sigma^{-m}$ is obtained, where σ is applied stress and t is rupture life, and the value of m is in the range 6-12. The gradient of the strain/time curve shown in Figure 1 was measured to time, and strain rate (%/hr)/time (hr) curve was plotted. The curves shown in Figure 3 were obtained under the stress of 39.2 MPa at 900°C (A) and 1000°C (B). For curve (B), time was noted in the upper line and strain rate was noted in the right side of the Figure. The strain rate of curve (B) was about 400 times as fast as curve (A), but it also changed with applied stress. If the creep rupture life is long, the strain rate/time curve becomes a figure like curve (A), that is, strain rate keeps decreasing until the latter period of creep, and it becomes slightly faster near rupture. Then it shows a decreasing tendency again, and at last the specimen rapidly deforms and ruptures. If the creep rupture life is short, the behavior is like curve (B), that is, strain rate becomes almost minimal in the beginning period; after that, it keeps increasing until rupture. In many cases like curve (B), the fact that the creep rate becomes fast and then slow before rapidly increasing was recognized as a precursory phenomenon.

Figure 4 shows log stress vs log minimum strain rate at 1000°C. The minimum creep rate was measured in the same way as Figure 3. From Figure 4, the relation of $\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n$ was obtained and n had a fairly large number 18; where $\dot{\epsilon}$ was the minimum creep rate, n was the power number. Generally, the dispersion strengthened alloy is characterized by the large number of n (2), (3).

Microstructure

Foil specimens for electron microscopy were prepared by using a multiwire cutting machine and by an electro-polishing method. In the machining, stainless wire of a 150 μm diameter and Cr₂O₃ powder of a 50 μm diameter were used. The thickness of slices was 400 μm. Electrolyte of 20% perchloric acid in methanol was used for the electro-polishing at 20°C. The voltage of stainless steel plate cathode was 20 V.

The substructure in Ni-1%Al₂O₃ specimens was observed by a Shimadzu SMH-5B electron microscope operated at 500 kV. The foil thickness was 0.5 μm - 1.0 μm. Photograph 1 (A) and (B) show the substructure in the extruded Ni-1%Al₂O₃ crystals and in the extruded-and-annealed Ni-1%Al₂O₃ crystals, respectively. In photograph 1 (A), small angle boundaries parallel to the direction of extrusion are observed. Many dislocation tangles are also observed around Al₂O₃ particles in grains (5, 6). In photograph 1 (B), new small angle boundaries non-parallel to the direction of extrusion are observed, besides the small angle boundaries parallel to the direction of extrusion. The dislocation tangles around Al₂O₃ particles have disappeared during the annealing at 1200°C for 5 hrs. [100] fiber texture was recognized in the extruded sample by X-ray analysis. This texture disappeared in the annealed sample.

Photograph 2 (A) shows the substructure in Ni-1%Al₂O₃ crystals crept at 900°C under a stress of 44.1 MPa. The rupture time was 35 hrs. Dislocation density in the grains is comparatively low, $1 \times 10^6/\text{cm}^2$. Photograph 2 (B)

shows the substructure in Ni-1%Al₂O₃ crystals crept at 1100°C under a stress of 41.6 MPa. The rupture time was 3 hrs. The dislocation density in the grains is high $1 \times 10^8/\text{cm}^2$. The dislocation tangles are observed around Al₂O₃ particles.

CONSIDERATIONS

Figure 1 showed both creep curves of the extruded and the annealed specimens for comparison. The strain and strain rate of the extruded specimen were larger than those of annealed specimen.

It was reported that the strength of the oxide dispersion strengthened alloy was improved by directionally applied heat treatment (4). However, according to our experiment, the creep strength was also improved by annealing at a high temperature, because the extruded specimen has high aspect ratio of the crystal grain (>4). Furthermore dislocation density was diminished by annealing.

From Figures 2 and 4, it is found that this alloy has a large stress dependency. When dislocation moves in Ni matrix, cell structures, grain boundary and so on are considered to be obstacles besides Al₂O₃ particles. However, the main obstacles should be Al₂O₃ particles having a good stability at high temperature. A large stress dependency of the creep behavior of the dispersion strengthened alloy is considered to relate to the particle size and interparticle spacing.

The n value in the relation $\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n$ was about 11 ~ 18, whereas the one measured by Wilcox for very finely dispersed Ni-ThO₂ alloy was 40 (3). It was due to the difference of particle size between both experiments.

In Figure 3 (A), the specimen tested at 900°C under a stress of 39.2 MPa was slowly hardening over about 350 hrs. Then it reached the minimum creep and soon ruptured. On the other hand, the specimen tested at 1000°C under the same stress rapidly showed minimum creep and the strain rate exponentially increased more and more until rupture.

Electron microstructure photographs of the creep ruptured specimens having different rupture times showed the difference in their dislocation structure. Glide of dislocations was important in the high creep rate, besides dislocation climb.

SUMMARY

1. The creep and creep rupture strength of an annealed specimen of Ni-1%Al₂O₃ dispersion strengthened alloy were measured under the applied stress of 20-50 MPa in a temperature range of 800-1100°C.
2. From these creep tests, a relationship of $t \propto \sigma^{-m}$ was obtained between creep rupture life t and the applied stress σ , where m was a power number and was in a range 6-12.
3. The relation of $\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n$ was obtained between creep strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ and applied stress σ , and the power number n was in a range 11-18.
4. The strain rate/time curve was obtained from the creep strain/time curve. They were parabolic. When the rupture life is short, the minimum part of the curve, namely the minimum creep rate, appears at the beginning of creep, while when the rupture life is long, the curve reaches the minimum creep rate after a work hardening for long period and soon rupture occurs.
5. The electron microstructure of the samples was observed before and after the creep test. The structure of the annealed specimen before the creep test consisted of grains of about 10 μm with little dislocation, and uniformly dispersed Al₂O₃ particles of less than 0.1 μm in size. The difference in dislocation structure was observed between the specimen having long rupture life and the one having short rupture life after the creep test.

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Figure 1 Creep Curves of the Extruded and the Annealed Specimens Under an Applied Stress of 39.2MPa at 800°C.

Figure 2 Creep Rupture Life–Applied Stress Relation for Annealed Specimens (logarithmic scale)

Figure 3 Creep Rate-Time Curve Under a Stress of 39.2MPa at 900°C (A) and 1000°C (B) for Annealed Specimens

Figure 4 Minimum Creep Rate-Applied Stress Relation at 1000°C for Annealed Specimens

(A) $1\mu\text{m}$

(B) $1\mu\text{m}$

Photograph 1 Substructures in Alloys Before Creep Test :
(A) Extruded, (B) Annealed at 1200°C, 5hrs.

(A) $1\mu\text{m}$

(B) $1\mu\text{m}$

Photograph 2 Substructure in Alloys After Creep Test :
(A) Applied Stress 44MPa, Temperature 900°C,
(B) Applied Stress 41MPa, Temperature 1100°C.